

THE ROLE OF THE PIANO IN KARAKALPAK SYMPHONY MUSIC

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Abstract. The piano has played a significant role among the performers in Karakalpak classical music up to the present day. Its significance lies not only in its place as an instrument, but also in its impact on the musical culture of any country in the world. The versatility of the piano has made it an essential tool in shaping the musical landscape. Throughout all stages of musical development, pianists, composers, conductors, and any other musician have worked in various fields. They have made it possible to open new horizons in the world of music.

Keywords: music, piano, symphony, performance, role, development, influence, instrument.

In Karakalpak classical music, the piano has undergone numerous innovations in its role up to the present day. Among these innovations are credit technologies, the use of economic functions, students, news, financial management, and development sectors. These innovations have given rise to the excellence of performers and their participation in new musical developments worldwide. The versatility of the piano has made it an essential tool in shaping the musical landscape [3]. Throughout all stages of musical development, pianists have worked in various fields. They have made it possible to open new horizons in the world of music.

The piano has been a part of Karakalpak symphony music since the early 20th century, when Russian and European influences began to shape the traditional music of this region. Pianists were among the first to introduce Western classical music to Karakalpak audiences, and they quickly became integral members of orchestras and ensembles.

One of the earliest and most influential pianists in Karakalpak classical music was Amanbay Tleubergenov. Born in 1905, Tleubergenov studied at the Moscow Conservatory and returned to his homeland to become a prominent performer, composer, and educator. He composed several works for piano and orchestra, including his Piano Concerto No. 1, which is considered one of the first examples of Karakalpak symphonic music [1].

Another notable figure in Karakalpak piano music is Nurgazy Tlendiyev, who was born in 1931. He studied at the Moscow Conservatory and became one of the most renowned pianists in the Soviet Union. Tlendiyev's performances of works by Russian and Western composers greatly influenced the development of Karakalpak classical music.

In addition to performing and composing, pianists in Karakalpak classical music have also played a crucial role in preserving traditional folk melodies and incorporating them into their works. One example is the pianist and composer Ayimkhan Nurmukhamedov, who has arranged and performed numerous pieces based on Karakalpak folk songs.

Today, the piano continues to be an essential instrument in Karakalpak symphony music. Pianists such as Ubaydullaeva and Charshemov are renowned for their performances of both classical and contemporary works. They have also collaborated with international musicians, bringing Karakalpak classical music to a global audience [2].

Conclusion. In conclusion, the piano has played a significant role in shaping Karakalpak symphony music. From its introduction in the early 20th century to its current status as an essential instrument, pianists have been at the forefront of innovation and excellence in this genre. Their contributions have not only enriched the musical culture of Karakalpakstan but also made a significant impact on the global classical music scene.

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